

Quantum Free Particle $\exp(ipx)$ With p Being Dynamic and x Static Part II

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In Part I, we noted that the classical probability expression $P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is velocity from $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)^2 + V(x) = E$ (1), sometimes appears in the literature. For $v(x) = \text{constant}$, $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length. This probability is based on the amount of time, dt , a particle spends in each dx . It could, however, just as well be the probability of finding a rest mass somewhere in L , i.e. there are no dynamics in $P(x)$, we argue.

The use of probability in classical mechanics is interesting because it is deterministic and should not have probability if one follows a particle with constant v through $x=vt$. Thus, as a first step, $P(x) = 1/L$ seems to mean that one is not following the particle in time so it may be anywhere in L and have a direction either to the right or left.

In Part I and previous notes, we have suggested a more consequential condition, namely that $P(x) = 1/L$ means that one has $Pd(p,x)Pd(-p,x)$ at each x for this to be equivalent to having a rest mass anywhere in L . In other words, one has a product probability for p and $-p$ at each x . A particle, however, has either p or $-p$, it cannot have both at the same time, but one does not follow the particle in time for $P(x)$. By breaking $P(x)$ into two factors, the sense of motion and direction appears, but a paradox seems to arise. One must have p at each x point, but at the same time probability is disappearing at x for p and $-p$ because momentum necessarily implies motion. A way to demonstrate decreasing probability together with a p at each x is to have a two dimensional probability such that the magnitude is 1, but each component shows a change in $Pd(p,x)$ which we call a dynamical probability. If one dimension decreases in probability, the other increases etc in a periodic manner. This leads to $Pd(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$ as a possible solution. This solution is unusual and does not seem to match classical observation, but it does explain two-slit interference which is also experimental as well as one dimensional reflection-refraction.

We suggest that if one uses a purely dynamical motion, $x=vt$, then there is no probability. The view of probability appears through the notion of p (and $-p$) being at each x at the same time that probability (in each dimension) changes at x , but in a different way for p and $-p$.

One may note that in real life problems, one has motion in one direction, e.g. interference from 2-slits or one dimensional reflection-refraction. These problems, however, cannot be solved using Newtonian mechanics. If one tries a probabilistic approach, we argue that it must be substantially different from the $x=vt$ view. We suggest that taking time out of the picture means that one must have p at each x and yet account for probability flow in one direction or the other. This leads to the concept of a wavelength and periodic probability. In such a case, x in $\exp(ipx)$ must be considered static.

Probability in Classical Mechanics

Classical Newtonian mechanics is deterministic and so it is not clear why a probability expression such as (1):

$$P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x) \text{ where } \frac{1}{2}mv(x)^2 + V(x) = E \text{ (nonrelativistic) ((1))}$$

should exist.

For $v(x)=\text{constant}$, $P(x)dx= dx/L$ ((2))

It seems that this probability ((2)) suggests that one does not follow a particle in time. Thus, it might be at any x and move in either to the right or left. More importantly, $P(x)=1/L$ describes a rest mass which may be at any x point in L . It seems that there should be no dynamics in $P(x)$ or a combined $p, -p$ at each x . If this is the case, there must be somehow the same probability to have p at each x , but given the sign of p , there is simultaneously probability flow in the direction of p . This seems to be a paradox which can be resolved by introducing two dimensions for the probability which must involve the variable x , because motion is in x . We use p because $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ etc and also represents impulse. Instead of having the same probability at each x , one may have the same modulus.

Thus: $P_d(p,x) = \text{component}_1(p,x) + i \text{component}_2(p,x)$ ((3))

The magnitude of ((3)) must be the same at each x because it is as if one has p at each x , but each component must demonstrate probability flow such that one has a sense of the direction of motion. If probability decreases in component 1, it increases in component 2.

Given that $P_d(p,x)$ must contain x to show probability flow in x , how does one reconcile it with $P(x)=1/L$? If $P_d(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$, then $P_d(px)P_d(-px)=\text{constant}$.

Thus, $P(x)=1/L$, where L is length, seems to suggest an AND condition for p and $-p$. Physically, however, a particle is moving either to the right or left, so $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-ipx)$ appears in a practical problem. $P(x)$, nevertheless, emerges in classical mechanical theory (1). It is proportional to dt , the amount of time spent in each dx , but if it is associated with p and $-p$ at the same time, there is no net momentum in each dx , only energy. Thus, $P(x)=1/L$ is associated with the same energy in each dx and not with any directional motion. It is thus a somewhat unusual quantity which indicates that each x carries the same weight, but in terms of an energy interpretation. We argue that this is like stating that one may have a rest mass m_0 at any x which is compatible with $P(x)$. $P(x)=1/L$ is thus a statement of translational invariance. It is not a probability which may be associated with physical motion which must occur in one direction or the other. We argue that this point is relevant for the square well potential.

Why Does One Need a Probabilistic View?

Classical mechanics does not use a probabilistic scenario, it is deterministic. Why does the statement $P(x)=1/L$ imply that there should be physical manifestations of probability, even in the classical world? We argued above that $P(x)=1/L$ is basically a statement of translational invariance, i.e. that p may be at any x with the same weight, but that there must exist a $P_d(px)$ showing probability flow in one direction or the other and this leads to a wavelength from $\exp(ipx)$. In Newtonian mechanics, acceleration occurs in dx which tends to zero, and so the

kinematics is determined in each dx . This kinematics is usually not probabilistic, i.e there is a potential $V(x)$ and $F=-dV/dx$ at x .

There is, however, a physical example which exists in the classical world which does involve probability and the breaking of translational symmetry in x , namely one dimensional photon reflection-refraction. This cannot be solved using Newtonian mechanics and involves a probability which does not seem to be associated with any randomness (probability) at the n_1 - n_2 junction (n =index of refraction). Nevertheless, there is probability in the problem which must be accounted for and cannot come from a deterministic Newtonian theory. This problem may provide justification for the $\exp(ipx)$ two dimensional probability view in that it allows for it to be solved. (Details are provided in Part I.) Another experiment which verifies $\exp(ipx)$ is n -slit interference-diffraction.

We note that the probabilistic view is the exact opposite of the deterministic one. The deterministic Newtonian picture must use time because the particle must change from one x to another in time. Thus, p is only at one x point at one time. The probabilistic picture insists on p having probability to be at each x point. If it were not, one would be following the particle in time (i.e deterministic motion). Yet, even in the probabilistic picture there must be probability flow in the direction of p . This probability type flow picture may then be used at junctions which break translational symmetry and introduce probability.

We note that in both the case of an n_1 - n_2 junction and an 2-slit device, translational symmetry is broken in space and associated with probability. In the n_1 - n_2 case, there is the probability to reflect or refract and in the 2-slit device, the probability to go through one slit or the other. These probabilities, however, exist because $\exp(ipx)$ already "carries" probability. Thus, the breaking of translational invariance with energy remaining unchanged is handled through a probabilistic approach. If one considers deterministic mechanics, a particle travels through one slit or the other without any probability considerations, but this does not match experimental results in the case that the slit width and separation are of the order of \hbar/p .

The Breaking of Translational Invariance, Probability and Uncertainty in X

The probabilistic approach using $\exp(ipx)$ leads to uncertainty in x because even though probability flows in one direction, one has p at each x . Thus, one does not know exactly where the particle is. This is a main idea of the probabilistic approach, we suggest, even for $P(x)$. If one knew where the particle was, then one would have a deterministic scenario. Thus, a probability view and uncertainty in x are directly linked. If one has translational invariance, one is not really worried if the particle is at one x or another because the environment is uniform in x . Such is not that case at a point of translational symmetry breaking. In such a case, the uncertainty in x may lead to the particle being at one place or another where the physical situation is different, such as in the case of an n_1 - n_2 junction or two -slits. As a result, there is a different probability for each case and this leads to summation of $\exp(ipx)$ s. Furthermore weights of $\exp(ipx)$ may be involved in probabilities as in the n_1 - n_2 junction case.

The Infinite Well Potential

There is no potential in the space between infinite potential walls. One may then ask: Why doesn't the classical $P(x)dx = dx/L$ apply? Physically, a particle must be either moving to the right or left if it is bouncing back and forth in a well. We have argued above that $P(x)$ means that one has the same energy at each x point. It does not describe the case of probability flow in one direction or the other. In the case of an n_1 - n_2 junction or 2-slit device, one must assume the same thing. The question is then: Why is a probabilistic rather than deterministic approach required? In classical mechanics, one may use deterministic physics to describe a particle bouncing back and forth in a well.

We argued above that $P(x)$ is linked with translational invariance and the potential walls seem to break this invariance. The idea of the $\exp(ipx)$ approach is to try to have probabilistic flow with p still being at each x point with the same magnitude of probability. Such an approach may be applied in the well scenario, but is particularly relevant for wells which are of the size of \hbar/p , the wavelength of $\exp(ipx)$. In the case of a non-infinite well potential, the uncertainty in x allows for probability to appear in that the particle may reflect or be transmitted, albeit with purely imaginary momentum. This again is like the n_1 - n_2 junction or 2-slit picture where the breaking of translational symmetry and the uncertainty in x allow for two different physical paths which are seen as probabilities, one to reflect and the other to tunnel.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to consider the meaning of $P(x)dx = dx/L$, which is called the classical probability expression for a particle moving with constant speed in the literature (1). (Actually, we suggest that $P(x)$ is not the probability of a moving particle, but rather the probability to have energy, such as a rest mass or p , $-p$ pair at each x point. The probability of a moving particle is something else which we call $P_d(p,x)$. It must contain x because there is probability flow in x in the direction of p and it cannot be constant because there is somehow the same probability for p to be at any x .)

Classical mechanics is deterministic so one may ask why one has probability in the first place. We argue that $P(x)$ makes sense as a probability if one does not follow the particle in time, i.e. gives up deterministic motion. In such a case, one simply says that the particle could be at any x point. The particle, however, does not even need to be moving in such a case. Thus, $P(x)$ could describe the probability to have a stationary particle at x . This would then be consistent with p and $-p$ AND probabilities at each x .

Physically, however, a particle moves either to the right or left in a dynamic situation so it seems that there is a paradox. The particle with p must be at each x with the same weight, but there must be probability flow in one direction or the other. This suggests two dimensional probability. Furthermore, the variable x should appear because there is probability flow in x , i.e. some probability leaves one dimension and enters the other, but this should be periodic. Thus, one may suggest that $P_d(px)P_d(-px) = P(x)$. Then $P_d(px) = \exp(ipx)$ is a solution. This solution, however, gives rise to a wavelength, i.e. uncertainty in x . This uncertainty in x is fine because one does not follow the particle in time. The issue, however, is that there are cases which break

translational symmetry such as an n1-n2 junction and 2-slit device. These allow for the particle to be in one or another physically different place and lead to the summation of $\exp(ipx)$.

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